

Solid-state fabrication of transparent YAG ceramics for optical applications: Characterization mixing, and processing of the starting oxides

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Polycrystalline yttrium aluminum garnet ceramic laser material ($Y_3Al_5O_{12}$) or YAG is one of the most common candidates that received much attention since 1995 due to its optical characteristics that has been improved greatly and its highly efficient laser oscillation that could be obtained [1]. Moreover, in the case of laser applications, some recent works demonstrated the rare-earth-doped YAG ceramics to be even better than the single crystals [2,3].

For the last thirty years, massive attention has been focused on the performance of YAG ceramics fabrication methods [4-7]. Compared with the complicated wet-chemical techniques of YAG nanopowders synthesis [8,9] the solid-state reactive sintering is considered as the easiest and cost efficient way for achieving of YAG desired properties. In this way, commercial high purity α - Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 powders are mixed in precise stoichiometric quantities where the required YAG phase formation occurs during the sintering step. It has been proved that the Al_2O_3 - Y_2O_3 system experienced three different crystallographic phases during the sintering. The phase composition and formation temperature ranges for each phase are described as follows [10]:

So, great attention has to be paid during the sintering reaction to avoid the presence of any secondary YAP or YAM phases which interfere with the YAG cubic structure and inhibit the propagation of light through the material thus strongly deteriorating the optical properties. Moreover, the most important issue in the transparent YAG ceramics is the removal of pores, which is achieved through the use of sintering additive and application of vacuum or pressure during sintering. Although tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) and MgO served as a common sintering additive for the densification promotion [11,12], the priority was given to the use of MgO where a successful fabrication of YAG transparent ceramic with excellent optical properties was achieved by employing a simple solid state reaction vacuum sintering using 0.03 wt. % MgO. The transmittance was 84.5% at 1064 nm, after sintering the sample at 1820°C for 8 h [12].

In the present study, commercial high purity α - Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 powders were mixed in precise stoichiometric quantities where the required YAG phase formation occurs during the sintering step. In addition, a small amount (0.03 wt.%) MgO or the equivalent amount of $Mg(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ was used both as a sintering aid and grain growth inhibitor. The mixed oxide suspensions were subjected to freeze granulation and freeze drying before uniaxial pressing at 30 MPa for 30 sec then cold isostatic pressing at 300 MPa for 5 min. Characterization of the starting oxide mixtures prepared by using of different methods, mixing conditions, and processing steps was carried out with the aim to achieve the optimum green body characteristics prior to the sintering process. Results revealed that both the phase composition and microstructure of the obtained YAG ceramics are noticeably affected by the factors such as morphology and particle size of the starting powders. Moreover, the

impact of pore size distribution, different shaping parameters, density of the green body, densification behavior of samples pre-sintered at 1675°C for 4h in air and those furtherly hot isostatically pressed at 1700°C for 4h and 200 MPa in argon atmosphere results were elucidated.

SEM of different YAG samples, YAG1 is sintering aid free, YAG2 is with 0.03 wt% of MgO, and YAG3 is with $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ equivalent to 0.03 wt% of MgO.

Keywords: Hot isostatic pressing, Solid-state reaction, YAG transparent ceramics.

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